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EMPOWERING WOMEN THROUGH EDUCATION IN INDIA

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Abstract

Education spreads along our lives from birth to death which fills our action with values, dignity, ethics and virtues. Human civilization moves along social, moral, cultural attributes. University Grants Commission (UGC), National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT), Central Board of Secondary Education (CBSE) regulates women education in India. Women Study Centers conduct studies on status, problems and issues on women education. Women illiteracy makes them deprived. Social, economic and political empowerment of women through education is the need of the day. This paper reviews various legislative and policy framework on women education in India.

Keywords: Education, Knowledge, Skills, University, UGC, Empowerment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is an instrument for self-reliance and selflessness. Aristotle said that education sound mind in a sound body to experience the power of supreme truth, goodness and beauty [1]. It provides women with knowledge, skills and self-confidence [2]. Empowerment challenges patriarchy to prevent discrimination [3]. Integration of women in economic development indicates improved social status [4]. The literacy rate of 82.14% among men and 65.46% among women created huge gap. Women literacy is low in rural. Illiterate women are subjected to divorce, desertion, domestic violence, child marriages, dowry, poverty, discrimination, abduction, rape, molestation etc. Women are constrained to domestic affairs but country demands their equal participation. The modern initiatives on Free and compulsory education, freedom to hold high offices, political rights has created changes. There is a need for encouraging women education in health care, nutrition, legal education, family welfare, self employment, vocational training suitable to the present requirements. Educating mothers is very important as they nourish, nurture and mould the character of the next generation.

2. POLICIES ON WOMEN EDUCATION

Government of India oriented on 'Promotion of welfare', 'Development' and 'Empowerment' philosophies. It initiated [5] University Education Commission, Secondary Education Commission (1952-53), The Central Social Welfare Board (1953), Condensed and Vocational Training Courses [6], University Grants Commission (1956), National Committee on Women Education (1958-59), Condensed Course for Adult Women (1958), Committee on

differentiation of Curriculum for Boys and Girls (1961), Correspondence Courses (1962), Committee to study the Public Support for Women Education (1963), Education Commission (1964-66), Committee on Status of Women (1971-74), Integrated Child Development Services (1975), Assistance to Voluntary Organisation (1982), The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) 1985, Department of Women and Child Development (1985), National Policy on Education (1986), Constitution of University at Puna, Padmavathi University at Tirupathi, Womens University Bijapur [7], National Literacy Mission (1988), 597 districts were covered under Total Literacy Campaigns [8], Mahila Samakhya Programme (1988), Introduced Legal education [9], Joint Council for Vocational Education (JCVE 1990), Programme of Action (1992), The Jan Shikshan Sansthan (JSS) was established impart vocational training [10], Teachers Education (1995), National Council for Teachers Education was constituted under National Council for Teacher Education Act, 1993 on the 17th August, 1995, Open and Distance Learning (ODL) and Teacher Education Institution are made to get Compulsory Accreditation in every 5 years from NCTE [11], The National Plan of action for the Girl Child (1991-2000) to prevent female foeticide, infanticide, discrimination, assault and abuse [12], Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (2000-2001) imposed moral obligation of providing primary education upon the parents, teachers, educational administrators and other stakeholders [13], Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya (2004) were constituted, National Curriculum Framework 2005 introduced three language formula for teaching regional, mother tongue, Hindi and English along with teaching through work by making teacher a facilitator with continuous appraisal system, Model School Scheme (November 2008) with special emphasize on health education, health checkups, special teachers, educational tours and NCC training to the students [14], Incentives to Girls for Secondary Education (May 2008) was introduced, National Means cum Merit Scholarship Scheme (May 2008) to be disbursed through the State Bank of India directly into student accounts on quarterly basis [15], Saakshar Bharat (September 2009) to build critical consciousness to face deprivations and disabilities [16], Right to Education (April 2010) through the Constitution (Eighty-sixth Amendment) Act, 2002 inserted Article 21-A into the Constitution to provide free and compulsory education for all children between 6 to 14 years as a Fundamental Right, Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (2016) policy was constituted.

3. WOMEN EDUCATION POLICIES FOR MINORITIES

National Institute of open Schooling (November 1989) was constituted. Open Basic Education by way of distance or continuing educational programme started. The Government initiated centrally sponsored School-based vocational education in 1988. National Commission for Minorities Educational Institutions (NCMEI 2004) was constituted with head quarters in Delhi. Nai Roshni The Scheme for Leadership Development of Minority Women (2012-13) scheme was started to benefit Muslim, Sikh, Christian, Buddhist and Parsi women notified under section 2 (c) of the National Commission for Minorities Act, 1992. Maulana Azad National Fellowship for Minority Students to provide integrated five years fellowship in the form of financial assistance to 756 students from minority communities with 30 per cent reservation to minority women every year notified by the Central Government to pursue M.Phil and Ph.D courses. UGC will select the candidates for award of scholarship in a transparent manner. UGC shall disburse the fellowship amount to the candidates through electronic clearance system (ECS) wherever feasible. The income ceiling of the parents/guardians of the candidate for this scholarship will be Rs.2.5 Lakh per annum. The quantum of fellowship for JRF and SRF will be at par with the UGC fellowship as amended from time to time. Maulana Azad National Scholarship Scheme for Meritorious Girl

Students of Minority was constituted to provide Scholarship to students passed S.S.L.C. exam and taking admission to 11th standard after declaration of 10th standard result for that year. Educational Loan from National Minorities Development Finance Corporation extends educational loans to facilitate job oriented education for the eligible persons belonging to Minorities. Maximum amount of Rs. 10 Lakhs is available at the rate Rs. 2 Lakhs per annum for technical and professional courses of durations not exceeding five years and Rs. 3 lakhs is for short duration cost intensive skill development training upto 01 year. Further for courses abroad, a maximum amount of 20 lakhs is available at Rs 4 lakhs per annum for any course with duration of maximum 5 years. Funds for this purpose are made available to the State Channelizing Agencies at an interest of 1% per annum to lend to the beneficiaries at 3% interest per annum. The loan shall be payable within five years after completion of the course.

4. CONCLUSION

It has recognized that sustainability in economic growth can be attained only through the equal participation of women in the development process of the country. The government began to direct its effort towards mainstreaming of women into the national development process by enacting various legislations to install equality, social justice and fraternity in the society [17]. The legislative and policy framework on education has facilitated the spread of education in the country. Gender disparity in literacy rates declined by 5.34 % points from 21.59 % prevailed in 2001 to 16.25 % in 2011 [18]. Gender equity can be promoted by changing the interaction at home, school, college, university and workplaces by creating favourable environment fostering the equality. The Ministry of Women and Child Development Government of India jointly instructed the Universities to implement 'Gender Champions' programme to recognize the leadership among women by the end of 2015. Extensive reforms in judicial mechanisms for responsive, sensitive administration of justice need to be attained. It is also very important to treat the loopholes of the related laws and check the execution procedures in detail.

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